
D6.3 / First report on project visibility and educational material

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DHU	Digital Health Uptake
DoA	Description of Action
CMFT	Comprehensive Motor Function Test
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HCPs	Healthcare Professionals
IT	Information Technology
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PD	Parkinson's Disease
R&I	Research and Innovation

Executive summary

This document is deliverable D6.3, “First report on project visibility and educational material”. It provides an overview of dissemination, communication, and networking activities carried out, along with the impact indicators and educational content developed up to M18 of the AI-PROGNOSIS project. The report highlights various approaches taken to enhance visibility and stakeholder engagement throughout the project. These include creating a distinct project identity, utilising various media platforms, engaging target audiences through multiple channels, and developing educational content to raise awareness about Parkinson's disease (PD).

The project has established a unified identity, ensuring consistency across all dissemination and communication channels. Regular updates shared via social media, newsletters, the project website, interviews, and conferences have kept stakeholders informed and engaged. Participation in scientific conferences, business events, and workshops has facilitated knowledge exchange, collaboration, and networking opportunities. Publications in peer-reviewed journals have further amplified the project's initial impact within the scientific community. Targeted communication activities have made project outputs visible to researchers, healthcare professionals (HCPs), industry representatives, people with or without PD, and the general public. Networking and clustering activities with sister projects, industry and other European initiatives have been initiated to foster collaboration, raise awareness, exchange knowledge, and communicate the project's vision and outcomes to key stakeholder groups.

In terms of educational content, the AI-PROGNOSIS project has prioritised the development of impactful and interactive materials to raise awareness about PD and improve health literacy. The content targets three main groups, namely: the general public, individuals without PD (including caregivers and those at risk), and people with PD. It emphasises early detection, treatment benefits, and lifestyle management while fostering trust in AI-enabled digital health tools. A new Learning Hub has been launched on the project's website, offering resources such as videos, articles, infographics, and quizzes, with plans for ongoing content expansion. All educational materials are developed collaboratively with input from relevant stakeholders, including HCPs and individuals with PD, ensuring accuracy, accessibility, and relevance. This multidisciplinary approach reflects AI-PROGNOSIS's commitment to delivering high-quality, user-focused resources.

The activities covered in this deliverable align with the dissemination and communication strategy detailed in deliverable D6.2, “Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan”, which defines the communication and dissemination strategy, key objectives and targeted dissemination and communication key performance indicators (KPIs) for the AI-PROGNOSIS project. This deliverable is part of Work package WP6, “Dissemination, communication and exploitation”, and is linked to Task 6.1, “Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring”, Task 6.2, “Clustering and networking activities”, and Task 6.3, “PD educational content development”. It serves as a periodic report on relevant activities and outputs. For future reporting, deliverable D6.5, “Midterm report on project visibility and educational material”, is scheduled for M32, and deliverable D6.6, “Final report on project visibility and educational material”, is planned for M48.

1 Introduction

Deliverable D6.3 is the first report on project visibility, networking, and educational material developed for the AI-PROGNOSIS project. It provides a detailed overview of the dissemination and communication strategy implementation. It details the activities carried out and the progress against the relevant key performance indicators (KPIs) achieved during the M1-M18 period of the project.

1.1 Document scope

Deliverable D6.3 is the third deliverable of WP6, “Dissemination, communication, and exploitation”. It provides a comprehensive overview of the dissemination, communication, and networking efforts over the first M18 period of the project. The report covers efforts to enhance project visibility, raise awareness, and develop educational materials focused on PD and health literacy. It also includes an evaluation of performance based on KPIs.

This deliverable is the product of Task 6.1, “Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring, Task 6.2, “Clustering and networking activities”, and T6.3, “PD educational content development”. Task 6.1, led by SSOL, is dedicated to the development, implementation and oversight of the dissemination and communication activities. It also focuses on building an active AI-PROGNOSIS stakeholder community to increase awareness and visibility of project results. Task 6.1 is closely linked with Task 6.2, led by SSOL, which focuses on clustering and networking activities to raise awareness and share project vision and outcomes with key stakeholders. Task 6.3, led by UU, aims at developing PD educational content in close collaboration with clinical partners from WP5. The overall objective of these tasks is to ensure the openness, visibility, and reuse of AI-PROGNOSIS outcomes through open science, effective dissemination and communication, and strategic networking activities.

This deliverable is closely related to deliverable D6.2, “Dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan”, which outlines the communication and dissemination strategy, approach, and KPIs. D6.3 provides a detailed account of the dissemination, communication and networking activities undertaken, showcasing the project's commitment to effective dissemination, impactful communication, and collaborative engagement.

1.2 Document structure

This document provides an overall view of dissemination, communication, networking activities, and educational material developed within the AI-PROGNOSIS project up to M18. The sections included are as follows:

- **Section 1** introduces the scope of the report, focusing on project visibility and educational materials.
- **Section 2** outlines the overall dissemination and communication strategy, including the target audience, project identity, and communication tools.
- **Section 3** describes project visibility efforts through media outlets, publications, and event participation, covering the project's website, social media presence, newsletters, and contributions from partners.
- **Section 4** covers the planning and development of PD educational content, including articles, videos, quizzes, and other materials.

- **Section 5** details clustering and networking activities, including partnerships, collaboration with sister projects, Horizon Results Booster services and partners networking efforts.
- **Section 6** evaluates the dissemination and communication performance based on KPIs.
- **Section 7** provides a summary of the main findings and conclusions drawn from the report.

2 Dissemination and communication approach

Deliverable D6.2, the “Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan”, details the dissemination and communication strategy, objectives and approach and serves as a background for planning and implementing the activities described in this deliverable.

2.1 Overall strategy

The AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination and communication strategy is designed to be dynamic and flexible, allowing adjustments based on feedback from various information providers, including consortium members and stakeholders. The main objectives of this strategy are:

- Disseminating scientific achievements of the project and making the outputs widely available for research and business purposes in the long-term;
- Informing key stakeholders about project objectives, progress, results and their innovation potential;
- Increasing awareness and engagement of people with and at risk of PD for addressing their issues and concerns to increase their awareness and build trust in new technology;
- Reaching similar and relevant R&I projects for promoting networking and joint activities;
- Establishing a forum/community for HCPs and authorities to develop new guidelines and standards.

Key features include:

- **Multi-faceted approach:** Balance between traditional academic channels, such as peer-reviewed journals, scientific conferences and workshops, with innovative communication methods, such as social media campaigns, quizzes, website articles, and videos, to reach a diverse audience and maximise impact.
- **Stakeholder-specific tailoring:** Messages are adapted for different audiences, including HCPs, policymakers, patients, and the scientific community.
- **Consistency and coherence:** Uniform messaging across channels to maintain a strong project image.
- **Diverse dissemination channels:** A mix of traditional and digital channels, including publications, events, open science practices, social media, website, and newsletters.
- **Interactive elements:** Infographics and interactive web content to boost engagement.
- **Synergies and networking:** Joint activities and collaborations to expand project reach.
- **Adaptability:** An agile strategy¹ that evolves with project developments and stakeholder feedback, with periodic reviews for ongoing improvements.

¹ <https://www.agilealliance.org/agile101/>

- Measurable outcomes: Progress tracking to ensure the dissemination and communication approach is both measurable and traceable.

The overall dissemination and communication approach is based on the following pathways:

1. **Publications** in peer-reviewed journals and business magazines;
2. **Dissemination events**, such as clinical, research and business conferences, workshops, special sessions, seminars and demo sessions to stakeholders;
3. **Media presence**, such as newsletters, website/blog, social media posts or local/national major media (TV and radio) presentations;
4. **PD educational content development**, such as tailored articles, including multimedia;
5. **Synergy and networking**, such as campaigns and organisation of/participation in events;
6. **Formulation of diversified messages, languages, and content** for different target audiences;
7. **Conception and design of a coherent project branding** to achieve an effective visual identity, including logo, infographics, and banners. Acknowledgements of EU funding, to be included in all materials relevant to communication, dissemination, Intellectual property rights (IPR) and major results;
8. **Set up of different communication channels:** the project website and social media accounts to be populated with project news and achievements, further contributing to the growth of its communities of interest and an open access publication archive within the Zenodo OpenAIRE public repository²;
9. **Preparation of diversified communication materials:** print-based (e.g., brochures, posters), multimedia (e.g., photos, teaser videos, interviews, demos), to be spread through website and social media.

This adaptive approach aims to engage stakeholders, communicate project objectives effectively, and achieve broad, impactful dissemination of AI-PROGNOSIS outcomes while aligning with Open Science principles³.

2.2 Target audience

AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination and communication actions target all relevant, interested, and potential audiences to maximise the project's impact across its various dimensions.

Based on the AI-PROGNOSIS project goals, the main target groups are:

- Persons with PD, their families, carers, and PD advocacy and research associations;
- The relevant primary and secondary HCPs⁴;
- The relevant scientific and technical community, i.e., clinical, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ethics research scientists and designers/developers of human-centred health technologies;
- The relevant industry leaders, e.g., mobile health (mHealth), medical AI, and pharmaceutical industry; and
- The healthcare enablers and policymakers.

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/openaire/about>

³ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about>

⁴ https://www.physio-pedia.com/Levels_of_Healthcare

A matrix outlining the dissemination and communication channels associated with each group's objectives is presented in **Table 1**.

Different dissemination and communication objectives are set for each stakeholder group. These include sharing scientific findings with researchers, collecting feedback from HCPs, collaborating with industry partners to promote the project vision, and fostering a PD-centred community among end users. Various channels, including scientific conferences, publications, events, demonstration sessions, newsletters, social media, the project website, and major media, such as articles in EU and national magazines, are foreseen to reach each target audience. This multi-faceted approach ensures that the project's goals and progress are effectively communicated to a broad and diverse audience.

Table 1 Stakeholder groups, their target audiences, objectives, and corresponding dissemination and communication channels

Main stakeholder groups	Stakeholder audience	Objectives	Dissemination & communication channels
Scientific community	Clinical, AI and ethics research scientists and designers/developers of human-centred health technologies	Communicate scientific findings and collect feedback; Transfer knowledge; Get support from the scientific community; Boost the project sustainability through the development of new related research projects; Extend network	Scientific conference presentations/posters; Publications in peer-reviewed journals; Events; Workshops; Special sessions; Seminars
Clinicians	Relevant primary/secondary health care professionals	Communicate scientific findings and collect feedback; Extend network; Communicate project progress and raise awareness regarding AI-PROGNOSIS solutions	Events; Workshops; Special sessions; Seminars
Industry	mHealth, medical AI, and pharmaceutical industry	Inform the industry about the project's vision and exchange ideas; Extend network; Demonstrate the business potential; push towards adoption of AI-PROGNOSIS products and services; Collect feedback on expectations and requirements to adjust	Business/Industry events and EXPOs stands/booths; Publication in business magazines; Demo sessions for stakeholders

		commercial exploitation plans; Emphasise the technical feasibility and competitiveness of concept and tools developed	
End-users	Persons with PD, their families, carers, and associations	Project involvement; Support engagement of the participants in the studies; Build a PD-centred community; Communicate project progress and raise awareness regarding AI-PROGNOSIS solutions	Demo sessions; Newsletters; Social media; Website; Major media presence
Policymakers	This is a wide group encompassing innovation driven local, regional, national authorities, representatives & associations, Ministries, parliaments and national & international Public Administrations	Project involvement; Attract the interest of relevant stakeholders	Website; Social media; Newsletters; Major media presence; Demo sessions
General public	The general public consists of a general audience and other actors not identified as direct targeted groups by the project, though this group can have strong interest in the project: citizen Interest Groups, NGOs, Community Action Groups	General awareness; Project progress	Website; Social media; Newsletters; Major media presence

2.3 Project identity

At the beginning of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, a unified branding identity was designed, including the project logo, colours, social media banners, templates and an animated logo video. These materials were distributed among partners and made available in the internal repository. Furthermore, the project logo and colour palette are easily accessible for dissemination and communication purposes on the project website within the “Newsroom” subpage “Communication Kit”⁵.

⁵ Logo and color palette, <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/communication-kit>

The AI-PROGNOSIS logo is an easily recognisable visual identity of the project, which depicts the project's title combined with the colourful profile picture. The latter has reference to the multifaceted character of an implied tulip icon, the landmark representation of PD⁶.

The logo design, in its standard usage format, is depicted in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 The AI-PROGNOSIS logo

There are further variations (**Figure 2** and **Figure 3**) for use in different contrast contexts – i.e., against dark or multicoloured photorealistic backgrounds. None of these variants detract from the logo's spirit or meaning.

Figure 2 Monochromatic blue variation of the AI-PROGNOSIS logo

Figure 3 Monochromatic white variation of the AI-PROGNOSIS logo

The AI-PROGNOSIS logo was designed to communicate several aspects of the project, including project identity, title and distinctiveness in a visually attractive, unique, and recognisable form.

The project's colour palette corresponds with the colours featured in the project's logo and is consistently applied across AI-PROGNOSIS templates and dissemination materials (**Figure 4**).

⁶ Van der Wereld named his prized flower, the 'Dr. James Parkinson' tulip, to honor the English apothecary surgeon who originally described PD in 1812.

Figure 4 The AI-PROGNOSIS colour palette

The primary purpose of establishing the colour palette for brand communications is to ensure a cohesive and distinct suite of messages that can be identified as originating from the brand. The colours were selected to maintain a professional and cohesive look, with attention to contrast for readability across digital and print media.

Moreover, an animated version of the project logo (**Figure 5**) was created to support social media and website communication efforts. This animated logo is utilised as an introductory element in various videos and video interviews, further reinforcing the project's visual identity.

Figure 5 The AI-PROGNOSIS logo animation

The animated logo video is accessible on the AI-PROGNOSIS YouTube channel⁷.

Dedicated banners (**Figure 6**) have been designed for all AI-PROGNOSIS social media profiles to ensure a solid appearance. The banners incorporate the project's colour palette, ensuring visual consistency with the overall brand style. Design harmony across all platforms ensures a professional project presentation and promotes effective engagement with the target audience.

Additionally, three essential templates for deliverables (**Figure 7**), meeting minutes (**Figure 8**) and presentations (**Figure 9**) were designed to ensure consistency in the consortium's project reporting and communication.

By maintaining a unified visual identity across all project materials and communication, we ensure that our message remains clear, coherent, and easily recognisable to our target audience.

⁷ AI-PROGNOSIS animated logo video, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ifLcl9-PHCU>

Figure 6 The AI-PROGNOSIS social media banners

Deliverable ID

Project acronym	AI-PROGNOSIS
Project full title	Artificial intelligence-based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis
Grant Agreement ID	10100561
Deliverable number	DI #
Deliverable title	Deliverable title in sentence case
Work package	WP# - WP title in sentence case
Deliverable type	[R - Document, report] or [DMP - Data Management Plan] or [DEM - Demonstration, pilot, prototype] or [DEC - Webinars, grant filings, videos, etc] or [OTHER]
Dissemination level	[PU - Public] or [SEN - Sensitive]
Version - date	## - DDMM/YYYY
Contractual delivery	Month YYYY
Actual delivery	Month YYYY
Lead partner	PARTNER SHORT NAME
Editor	Person Full Name (PARTNER SHORT NAME)
Contributors	Person 1 Full Name (PARTNER SHORT NAME); Person 2 Full Name (PARTNER SHORT NAME)
Reviewed by	Full name of Reviewer 1 (PARTNER SHORT NAME) Full name of Reviewer 2 (PARTNER SHORT NAME)
Approved by	Leonios Hadjiontidis (AUTH, Project Coordinator)
Keywords	[in alphabetical order] A keyword, B keyword, ...

Figure 7 AI-PROGNOSIS deliverable template

Meeting minutes

[Plenary meeting #] or [WP# meeting #] or [Title of meeting]		
Date(s)	Place	Organiser(s)
DD Month YYYY	[City, Country] or [Online]	PARTNER SHORT NAME
Version -date	Dissemination level	
## - DDMM/YYYY	SEN - Sensitive	

Document history

Version	Date	Minute contributors	Action / status
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...
2.0	DDMM/YYYY	PARTNER SHORT NAME 1; PARTNER SHORT NAME 2;	Approved minutes

Attendees

Full name	Partner	Notes
...	...	E.g. Left the meeting before Agenda item 2
...

Agenda

- Agenda item 1
- Agenda item 2
- ...

Minutes

3.1 Agenda item 1

Statements

- ...

Or write 'None'

Decisions

- ...
- ...

Or write 'None'

Action items

#	Description	Responsible	Due date
#	Action item short description ...	PARTNER	DDMM/YYYY
#

Or delete table and write 'None'

Notes

Any notes go here or write 'None'

3.2 Agenda item 2

Statements

- ...

Or write 'None'

Decisions

- ...
- ...

Or write 'None'

Action items

#	Description	Responsible	Due date
#	Action item short description ...	PARTNER	DDMM/YYYY
#

Or delete table and write 'None'

Notes

Any notes go here or write 'None'

Figure 8 AI-PROGNOSIS Minutes of meeting template

Figure 9 AI-PROGNOSIS presentation template

2.4 Communication kit

At the beginning of the project, in M1-M3, a communication kit was developed, which includes a project poster, flyer, and roll-up poster⁸. These materials reflect the project’s brand and present a summary of key information about the project. In **Figure 10** the AI-PROGNOSIS flyer and poster are presented, respectively.

The project flyer/poster is intended to be used in various contexts to promote and raise awareness about the AI-PROGNOSIS project, including conferences, workshops, various events and presentations. A roll-up banner is intended to be used as a promotional and informative tool at events, conferences, exhibitions, workshops, and other public events.

The materials are easily accessible for dissemination and communication purposes on the project website within the Newsroom subpage Communication Kit⁹.

To date, the roll-up banner and poster have been used in the 2nd plenary meeting and King’s Parkinson’s Charitable Fund’s Inaugural Event (**Figure 11**).

⁸ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/communication-kit>

⁹ Promo materials, <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/communication-kit>

Figure 10 AI-PROGNOSIS Poster (on the left) and Roll-up banner (on the right)

Figure 11 AI-PROGNOSIS poster (on the left) and roll-up (on the right) displayed at events

3 Project visibility

3.1 Media

AI-PROGNOSIS utilises various media-based communication to increase project visibility, disseminate results, raise awareness, attract interest and offer information to various stakeholders. This communication is based on four different activities, namely:

- Website posts;
- Social media posts;
- Newsletters; and
- Major media (TV/radio).

Communication efforts through the project website and social media channels have been ongoing since the beginning of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, ensuring continuous engagement and dissemination of project-related information.

3.1.1 Website

The AI-PROGNOSIS website¹⁰ serves as the main platform for presenting the project to external stakeholders, sharing its main objectives, and showcasing results and achievements. It was launched in M3, and its development rationale was thoroughly described in deliverable D6.1, "Project branding and communication channel".

The AI-PROGNOSIS website (**Figure 12**) is linked with social media platforms, providing seamless integration between the website and social media channels. This enhances the project's online presence and extends its reach to a broader audience.

The website is visually appealing and has a flexible structure that allows sections to be added or removed as needed. Since its launch, new sections and subsections have been introduced to reflect project needs, including:

- **Learning Hub** for PD educational content, featuring **Articles, Dictionary, Videos** and **Quiz** subsections.
- **People** subsection under the About section to introduce the project team (**Figure 12**).
- **Networking** subsection under the Research section to showcase related projects (**Figure 12**).

The website is frequently updated, with an average of 4 posts per month, covering news, event participation, publications and project developments. It also includes downloadable materials and newsletters (**Figure 13**).

On average, over the M1-M18 period, the website received 183 visitors per month, which is below the planned KPI of 1,000 visitors per month (**Figure 14**). One contributing factor to this shortfall is compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹¹, which governs the processing of personal data and emphasises the protection of individual privacy rights. Under GDPR, websites must obtain explicit consent from users before placing cookies that process personal data on their devices. This consent must be freely given through affirmative action, such as clicking an "Accept" button. These provisions are detailed in Article 6 (Lawfulness of processing) and Article 7 (Conditions for consent) of GDPR.

¹⁰ The AI-PROGNOSIS website, <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/>

¹¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>

Figure 12 The AI-PROGNOSIS website – Home page (left), People page (centre), and Networking page (right)

Figure 13 Newsroom section on the AI-PROGNOSIS website

Date ↑	Page views	Site sessions ⓘ	Unique visitors
Summary	1,368	339	127
01/07/2023	164	23	8
01/08/2023	529	92	18
01/09/2023	323	91	51
01/10/2023	142	46	34
01/11/2023	95	42	24
01/12/2023	115	45	23
01/01/2024	142	52	32
01/02/2024	121	44	30
01/03/2024	110	41	29
01/04/2024	180	100	87
01/05/2024	239	175	134
01/06/2024	78	28	17
01/07/2024	38	24	15
01/08/2024	79	34	16
01/09/2024	108	39	20
01/10/2024	522	128	44
01/11/2024	47	22	13

Figure 14 Website analytics, from July 2023 to November 2024

Due to GDPR requirements, Wix's¹² traffic reports only include data from visitors who have accepted the cookie consent policy. This limitation reduces the availability of a complete traffic report, thereby impacting overall visibility metrics.

Additionally, from M1 to M18, the project was primarily in the development phase, with limited significant scientific and tangible results available and PD educational content still under development.

However, the introduction of the Learning Hub section and the first quiz on the website in October 2024, positively impacted visibility metrics, as shown in **Figure 14**. The number of visitors increased to 522 during that month. This progress underscores the project's motivation to continue developing and expanding the Learning Hub section with PD educational content.

To increase website visibility and number of visitors, 5-day Google ads campaigns were launched in M10 and M11 (**Figure 15**). The campaign from April 28 to May 5, 2024, resulted in 966 clicks and 73,406 impressions¹³. The campaign from May 26 to May 31, 2024, resulted in 706 clicks and 38,843 impressions. These campaigns generated a significant number of impressions and clicks over a short time period, indicating increased visibility and engagement with the AI-PROGNOSIS website.

¹² The website platform used for creating and maintaining the AI-PROGNOSIS website.

¹³ Impressions definition, <https://support.google.com/google-ads/answer/6320?hl=en>

Campaign performance 28 April 2024 - 6 May 2024					Campaign performance 26 May 2024 - 31 May 2024				
Campaign	Campaign state	Campaign type	Clicks	Impr.	Campaign	Campaign state	Campaign type	Clicks	Impr.
ai-prognosis0	Paused	Search	966	73,405	ai-prognosis0	Paused	Search	706	38,843

Figure 15 Google ads campaign results, April – May 2024

As the AI-PROGNOSIS project progresses and more tangible results are produced, starting from M19, the organic flow of visitors is expected to increase. This growth is anticipated to be further supported by the integration of educational content presented in a more engaging manner, boosting both interest and visitor numbers.

3.1.2 Social media

Social and digital media are important in raising awareness about the AI-PROGNOSIS project and showcasing its progress. AI-PROGNOSIS is currently active on 5 social media platforms, in particular: LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube (**Table 2**).

Table 2 Social media channels

Social media channel	Handle in the channel	Reference
LinkedIn	@ai-prognosis	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ai-prognosis/
X (formerly Twitter)	@ai prognosis	https://twitter.com/ai prognosis
Facebook	@AI-PROGNOSIS	https://www.facebook.com/AIPROGNOSIS
Instagram	@ai prognosis	https://www.instagram.com/ai prognosis/?next=%2F
YouTube	@AI-PROGNOSIS	AI-PROGNOSIS - YouTube

The presence on social media is a significant tool for disseminating AI-PROGNOSIS results, enabling the project to:

- To create awareness;
- Promote AI-PROGNOSIS identity and build a strong reputation;
- Engage and encourage stakeholders and the public in dialogue; and
- Disseminate project news, results, actions and events.

The AI-PROGNOSIS LinkedIn, X and Facebook accounts were established from the beginning of the project and are the main project communication channels. YouTube and Instagram were introduced in M7, respectively, to support engagement with visual content and broader audience interaction.

Social media channels have been branded with the project look and feel following brand identity guidelines. To date, AI-PROGNOSIS has 1,107 followers across all social media accounts (**Figure 16**), and the number is steadily growing. Since M6, the total number of followers has grown over 3 times.

Figure 16 Number of AI-PROGNOSIS followers on social media channels

To maintain engagement, at least 2 posts are made per week across the main project channels, namely: LinkedIn, X and Facebook. Social media accounts are linked with the AI-PROGNOSIS website and accessible by clicking on the corresponding social media icons on the project's website.

The AI-PROGNOSIS project remains flexible in its platform choices to ensure effective outreach. Alternative platforms such as Bluesky, Mastodon, or others may be considered in the future based on their relevance and engagement potential with the target audience.

3.1.2.1 LinkedIn

To date, the project's LinkedIn account has been the most active social media channel of AI-PROGNOSIS (**Figure 17**). The page currently has 646 followers from a wide variety of industries, including but not limited to:

- Higher education;
- Research services;
- Software development;
- IT services and IT consulting;
- Hospitals and healthcare;
- Biotechnology research; and
- Medical equipment manufacturing.

A total of 132 posts have been published on LinkedIn, not including reposts. To maintain engagement, on average 2 posts are made per week. Content includes AI-PROGNOSIS project updates, event participation, interviews with project members, key achievements, partners' activities, communication on sister projects activities, interactive educational content and external content, such as various scientific and other publications relevant to the project topic (**Figure 18**).

Figure 17 AI-PROGNOSIS LinkedIn profile

Figure 18 Examples of AI-PROGNOSIS Presence on LinkedIn

3.1.2.3 Facebook

AI-PROGNOSIS maintains a Facebook page (Figure 20) to reach a broader and less specialised audience. The project's Facebook page includes news, photos and information about the project, its developments and activities.

The page currently has 24 followers. It should be noted that Facebook's presence is low for most R&I EU projects, mainly due to the audience of this medium.

Figure 20 AI-PROGNOSIS Facebook profile

To increase visibility and engagement, AI-PROGNOSIS has joined several Parkinson's-focused communities, including Parkinson's Disease Awareness, Support, Cure Hope @togetherforsharon (3.0K members), Living With Parkinson's Disease (3.5K members), and Parkinson's Group (13.8K members). These platforms provide an excellent opportunity to connect with people living with PD and those interested in advancing PD care. Dedicated educational content tailored to the needs and interests of these groups has already been shared, aiming to further boost engagement (Figure 21).

Figure 21 Examples of interactions across Parkinson's support groups

3.1.2.4 Instagram

The AI-PROGNOSIS Instagram account (**Figure 22**) was created in M7 to support engagement with visual content and broader audience interaction. The page focuses on sharing educational materials, updates, and interactive content related to the project. It currently has 103 followers. The number of followers has increased by over 1.5 times since M12, growing from 68 to 103 followers, reflecting steady growth.

Figure 22 AI-PROGNOSIS Instagram profile

Over the period from 21 August to 18 November 2024, the AI-PROGNOSIS Instagram account has reached 366 unique accounts, with the majority of engagement (86.3%) coming from non-followers (**Figure 23**). This demonstrates strong visibility and the potential to attract a broader audience. Posts remain the primary content type, with a total of 489 views over the period. Notably, QR-code-driven posts performed exceptionally well, with the top post on November 6, 2024 reaching 246 accounts, highlighting the effectiveness of actionable and interactive content in engaging users.

Figure 23 AI-PROGNOSIS Instagram account performance

By building on the current strengths, such as posts and QR-code-driven content, and improving underperforming areas, such as reels, the AI-PROGNOSIS Instagram account can further enhance its audience reach and engagement.

3.1.2.5 YouTube

YouTube serves as a platform to post and promote dynamic media content (videos) developed over the course of the project. The AI-PROGNOSIS YouTube channel (Figure 24) was launched in M7 to showcase the project in an audiovisual format. Currently, the channel has 18 subscribers and features 4 video interviews with the project coordinator and clinical partners, as well as 1 short video dedicated to Parkinson's Awareness Month 2024. Additionally, video (interview) material gathered at the second plenary meeting will generate future videos.

Figure 24 AI-PROGNOSIS YouTube channel

We aim to increase the channel's visibility and engagement through active cross-promotion on social media and the project website, ensuring broader dissemination of project updates and key achievements.

3.1.3 Newsletter

The AI-PROGNOSIS newsletter (**Figure 25**) has been issued quarterly, starting from M3. To date, 4 newsletters have been published. The content is presented in accessible language, tailored for the general public and includes summaries of the latest project news, past and upcoming project events, interviews with the project partners, and other activities and initiatives related to the project.

Figure 25 AI-PROGNOSIS newsletters

A sign-up form for the newsletter is on the project website. To date, 40 subscriptions have been made via the website (**Figure 26**).

Figure 26 Number of newsletter subscribers through the website

The newsletter is available in PDF format, making it accessible both online and offline. It is distributed via Wix Email marketing and promoted on the project's social media channels and website¹⁴ to ensure broad accessibility and dissemination. The delivery statistics for the fourth project newsletter (**Figure 27**) show a high open rate of 72%, reflecting strong interest in our updates. A click rate of 33% shows that a significant portion of our audience interacts with the links provided. These metrics reflect substantial interest and interaction with the newsletter's

¹⁴ AI-PROGNOSIS project newsletters, <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/newsletters>

content, despite a smaller subscriber base. Promotion through additional channels further amplifies its reach and supports the project's dissemination objectives.

Figure 27 Delivery statistics of the AI-PROGNOSIS 4th newsletter

With the second newsletter edition, a LinkedIn newsletter (Figure 28) was introduced in M10 to increase the number of subscribers.

Figure 28 AI-PROGNOSIS LinkedIn newsletter

To date, 367 subscriptions have been made via LinkedIn, contributing to a total of 407 newsletter subscribers, including 40 subscriptions from the project website (Figure 29). This marks a 38.5% overall growth in subscribers since M12, with LinkedIn growing by 25% and website subscriptions increasing by 82%.

Figure 29 Number of AI-PROGNOSIS newsletter subscribers

Additionally, the AI-PROGNOSIS newsletter is made available through the Zenodo OPENAIRE public repository¹⁵, ensuring access to a wider audience, including researchers, stakeholders and the general public. This further enhances the dissemination and impact of the project's results (**Figure 30**).

Figure 30 AI-PROGNOSIS Newsletter on Zenodo

These efforts ensure that the AI-PROGNOSIS project remains transparent and engaging to a broad audience, effectively promoting its activities and results. Moving forward, the AI-PROGNOSIS project will continue to refine newsletter content and distribution strategies to maximise outreach and impact, ensuring that stakeholders remain well-informed about the project's progress and achievements.

3.1.4 Major media

Up to M18, no major media (TV/radio) presence was achieved. Major media engagement is planned to commence once tangible results have been produced and can be showcased.

3.1.5 Contribution of partners to online visibility

Aligned with the AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination and communication strategy, AI-PROGNOSIS consortium members have actively promoted the project through various communication channels, including social media, websites, newsletters, and other outreach initiatives. These efforts aimed to broaden awareness of AI-PROGNOSIS and engage diverse stakeholders, such as the scientific community, clinicians, industry professionals, end-users, and the general public.

During the reporting period, project partners' posts and reposts on social media platforms generated significant impressions, reactions, and engagement. Updates shared by AI-PROGNOSIS consortium members included project milestones, events, and key research developments (**Table 3, Figure 31**). In addition to social media, project partners have highlighted AI-PROGNOSIS through articles published on institutional websites, presenting the project's objectives, goals, and ongoing progress. Additionally, newsletters featuring project updates were distributed to targeted audiences, including employees, clinicians, and stakeholders, achieving broad regional and international reach (**Figure 32**).

¹⁵ Zenodo OPENAIRE public repository, <https://zenodo.org/me/uploads?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

AI-PROGNOSIS / D6.3 First report on project visibility and educational material

Figure 31 AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination on partners' social media

Figure 32 AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination on partners' websites and newsletters

The table below (**Table 3**) provides an overview of the online communication activities undertaken by the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium partners, including the type of activity, target audiences, communication channels, and outreach levels.

Table 3 List of partners' online communication activities

Partner	Description/Communication channel	Target audience	Reach	Link
AUTH	Reposted over 20 posts via the Signal Processing and Biomedical Technology Unit (SPBTU) AUTH LinkedIn account (600 followers)	Scientific community Industry	100 impressions on average 10 reactions on average	(1) Signal Processing & Biomedical Technology Unit - AUTH: Posts LinkedIn
UU	Website article	Scientific community		https://www.uu.se/en/department/womens-and-childrens-health/research/digital-health-and-mental-health-unit/participatory-ehealth--health-data-research-group-pehr/ongoing-projects/ai-prognosis
CERTH	Website	Scientific community Industry General public		https://vcl.itl.gr/projects/artificial-intelligence-based-parkinsons-disease-risk-assessment-and-prognosis/
FMH	Posts on social media (LinkedIn);	Scientific community Industry General public		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/faculdade-de-motricidade-humana-abril-%C3%A9-om%C3%AAs-de-conscientiza%C3%A7%C3%A3o-da-doen%C3%A7a-activity-7188152814940942337-mwOf?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
DBC	Posts on social media (LinkedIn)	Industry General Public Scientific community		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/diadikasiagr_april-is-parkinsons-awareness-month-activity-7184520692774686720-xdrl?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop https://www.linkedin.com/posts/diadikasiagr_parkinsonsdisease-parkinsons-digitalhealth-activity-7138901725691777024-

				qLLX?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
SSOL	10 LinkedIn newsletter editions	Industry Scientific community General public	141 subscribers	https://www.linkedin.com/new/sletters/7157738790088790016/
AING	Website Social media	Industry Scientific community		https://ainigma.tech/projects/ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ainigma-technologies_parkinson-parkinsonsdisease-artificialintelligence-activity-7169249058216259585-GlJd?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
NTD	Posts on social media	Industry Scientific community General public		(2) Post LinkedIn https://www.linkedin.com/posts/arnfin-bergmann-md-2b410a13_neurotransdata-parkinson-euproject-activity-7085569535268765697-N_ob/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
UOXF	Posts on social media (LinkedIn)	Scientific community General public		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7263319449531822080/?actorCompanyId=98145694
SQD	Posts on social media (LinkedIn)	Scientific community General public		(2) Post Feed LinkedIn
FIN	Website article	Scientific community Clinicians		https://www.fundacionince.com/investigacion/
CING	Article on website	Scientific community Clinicians		https://www.cing.ac.cy/en/news-113/media-releases/oct23_prognosis https://www.cing.ac.cy/en/news-113/media-releases/may24_ai_seminar
CHUT	Posts on social media (LinkedIn)	Scientific community Clinicians General Public	946 impressions 222 clicks 16 reactions 1 comment 2 republications	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206309220508430336/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206309220508430336/
CHUT	Presentation of the project on the CHU	Scientific community Clinicians	101 views	https://www.chu-toulouse.fr/ai-prognosis

	de Toulouse's website	General Public Authorities		
CHUT	Post in newsletter Recherche (CHU de Toulouse)	CHU de Toulouse employees (scientific community, general public, clinicians)	Sent to 1390 people	
INTRA	Article on the website	Industry General public		https://www.netcompany-intrasoft.com/news/netcompany-group-showcase-innovative-healthcare-it-solutions-medica-2023-dusseldorf

3.2 Publications

3.2.1 Scientific publications

The project aims to publish at least 20 scientific publications targeting Q1 journals to communicate scientific findings. The project will ensure Open Access, with free-of-charge online access for any user to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. Scientific publications are planned to start from M18 once solid scientific results are available.

To date, 4 scientific publications have been published, in particular:

- Alves, B., Alhussein, G., Carnide, F., Grammalis, N., Dimitropoulos, K., Trivedi, D., Kurtis Urra, M., Hadjidimitriou, S., Hadjileontiadis, J. L., & Dias, S. B., (2024). An agile co-creation approach for designing a comprehensive digital motor assessment test for Parkinson's Disease patients. In *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Software Development and Technologies for Enhancing Accessibility and Fighting Info-exclusion (DSAI 2024)*. Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates, 13-15 November 2024.
- A. Stergioulas, S. B. Dias, B. Alves, G. al Hussein, S. Bostantjopoulou, Z. Katsarou, I. Dagklis, N. Grammalidis, K. Dimitropoulos (2024, June). Assessing motor skills in Parkinson's Disease using smartphone-based video analysis and machine learning. In *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments (PETRA 2024)* (pp. 562-568). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3652037.3663945>
- Ziogas, I., Lamprou, C., & Hadjileontiadis, L. J. (2023). Bispectral Analysis of Parkinsonian Rest Tremor: New Characterization and Classification Insights Pre-/Post-DBS and Medication Treatment. *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 114459-114474, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3324987>
- Alves, B., Mota, P. R., Sineiro, D., Carmo, R., Santos, P., Macedo, P., ... & Pereira, C. M. (2024). MoveONParkinson: developing a personalized motivational solution for Parkinson's disease management. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12, 1420171. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1420171>

Additionally, several publications have been prepared for submission:

- Saad, A., Gerasimou, I., Lyreskog, D., Hadjidimitriou, S., de Vos, M., Drivas, I., Zaras, J., Stergioulas, A., Bensenousi, A., Hadjileontiadis, L., Chatzichristos, C., on behalf of

the AI-PROGNOSIS Consortium (2024). A Framework for Trustworthy AI in Healthcare through the AI-PROGNOSIS Project. (To be submitted);

- Dias, S.B., Alhussein, G., Alves, B., Fabbri, M., Rascol, O., Menargues, M., Kurtis Urrea, M., Grammalidis, N., Dimitropoulos, K., Hadjidimitriou, S., Hadjileontiadis, L.J., on behalf of the AI-PROGNOSIS Consortium (2024). AI-driven Cognitive and Motor Digital Assessment of Parkinson's Disease: a Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Lancet Digital Health* (to be submitted);
- Dias, S. B., Alves, B., Alhussein, G., Menargues, M., Kurtis Urrea, M., Grammalidis, N., ... & Hadjileontiadis, J. L. (2024). AI-based Parkinson's risk, progression, and medication response: a narrative review. *npj Digital Medicine* (to be submitted);
- Luckhaus, J., Riggare, S., Kharko, A., Blease, C., Hägglund, M., Scott Duncan, T., on behalf of the AI-PROGNOSIS Consortium (2024). Co-designing a “win-win” in predictive AI: Insights from interviews and focus groups with persons with Parkinson's Disease. Conference paper for Medical Informatics Europe 2025;
- Luckhaus, J., Scott Duncan, T., Kharko, A., Blease, C., Hägglund, M., Riggare, S., on behalf of the AI-PROGNOSIS Consortium (2025). *Title to be confirmed*. *Journal of Medical Internet Research (JMIR) mHealth and uHealth* (To be submitted).

These forthcoming publications represent significant progress towards meeting the project's publication objectives and aim to disseminate its scientific findings widely.

3.2.2 Publications in business magazines

No publications in business magazines were considered up to M18 of the project. Publication in these outlets is foreseen from M18, when solid scientific results will be available. It is expected to publish at least 4 publications in business magazines.

3.3 Events

Events are one of the most important parts of the dissemination and communication strategy. They allow the project to connect with stakeholders and the general public, encourage networking and show advances and results of the project. Events also feed the content of the communication channels and tools (website, social media, newsletters), generating great impacts on different audiences.

The strategy of participation in events is set up at four different levels, more specifically: scientific conferences, business/industry events, workshops/seminars/special sessions, and clinical focus groups. It is expected project partners to participate in at least:

- **20 scientific conferences;**
- **3 business/industry events/EXPOSs stands;**
- **8 workshops/sessions/seminars; and**
- **6 demo sessions to stakeholders.**

During the reporting period, project partners participated in:

- **Scientific conferences:** Engaged in 10 conferences, including the 4th National Congress of Parkinson's Disease and Movement Disorders, CRISP - EUROPAR Patient Group Meeting, V JORNADAS DE PARKINSON (5th Parkinson's Days), PETRA 2024, 13th Movement Disorders Teaching Course, IRBDSG Annual Meeting 2024, King's Parkinson's Charitable Fund's Inaugural Event, NeuroconexiON: Second Edition, DSAI 2024, and the 2nd Healthy Longevity Symposium.
- **Business/Industry Events:** Participated in Medica 2023. Additionally, the project team engaged in 5 business-focused events, including meetings with Pfizer's Centre

for Digital Innovation (Thessaloniki, Greece), Sonova International (Zurich, Switzerland), KOIOS Care (Antwerp, Belgium), Neuralight (Tel Aviv, Israel) and ELPEN Pharmaceutical Co. (Athens, Greece).

- **Workshops/Seminars/Special Sessions:** Organised the "AGENT" workshop at PETRA 2024; presented the project to PhD students at Faculdade de Motricidade Humana (Lisbon, Portugal) as part of the Physical Activity and Health programme; introduced the project during the "Neuroscience and Neurodegeneration" MSc programme at AUTH (Thessaloniki, Greece); and showcased the project at Europe Biobank Week and the PMNET Forum.
- **Demo sessions to stakeholders:** 2 initial co-creation sessions were held during the reporting period, engaging PD patient representatives to gather feedback and refine the design and usability of the project's digital tools. These sessions gathered valuable feedback to refine the design and usability of the Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT) and the mAI-Care app, marking the first steps in engaging stakeholders with the project's tools.

Detailed descriptions of these events are presented below in subsections 3.3.1- 3.3.4.

3.3.1 Scientific conferences

During the reporting period, the AI-PROGNOSIS project has been presented at 10 scientific conferences, in particular:

1. **4th National Congress of Parkinson's Disease and Movement Disorders** (9–11 November 2023, Brasov, Romania)
 - Presented by Dr Dhaval Trivedi (KCL), highlighting AI-PROGNOSIS project updates at an event organised by the Parkinson's Disease and Movement Disorders Society, the Pro Neurology Association, and the Transilvania University of Braşov (**Figure 33**).

Figure 33 Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project at the 4th National Congress of Parkinson's Disease and Movement Disorders

2. **CRISP - EUROPAR Patient Group Meeting** (20 February 2024, London, UK)
 - Dr. Dhaval Trivedi (KCL) shared insights into AI-PROGNOSIS and its contributions to public and patient involvement through CRISP, EUROPAR's expert patient group.
3. **The 13th International Movement Disorders Teaching Course** (14–16 March 2024, Brasov, Romania)
 - Presented by Dr Dhaval Trivedi (KCL), focusing on artificial intelligence (AI) for Parkinson's prediction (**Figure 34**).

Figure 34 Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project at the 13th International Movement Disorders Teaching Course

4. **V JORNADAS DE PARKINSON (V Parkinson's Days)** (19 April 2024, Galicia, Spain)
 - Dr María Luisa Almarcha Menargues (FIN) presented the project and discussed AI's transformative benefits for Parkinson's treatment and diagnosis (**Figure 35**).

Figure 35 Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project at the V Jornadas de Parkinson

5. **IRBDSG Annual Meeting 2024** (19–21 June 2024, Oxford, UK)
 - Prof. Maarten De Vos (KUL) presented the abstract “Parkinson’s Disease Progression Using RBD Biomarkers”, focusing on digital biomarkers for REM sleep behaviour disorder (**Figure 36**).

Figure 36 Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project at the IRBDSG Annual Meeting 2024

6. King's Parkinson's Charitable Fund's Inaugural Event (21 June 2024, London, UK)

- Dr Dhaval Trivedi (KCL) shared insights on the project and AI's role in predicting Parkinson's disease progression (**Figure 37**).

Figure 37 Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project at the King's Parkinson's Charitable Fund's Inaugural Event

7. PETRA 2024 (26–28 June 2024, Crete, Greece)

- Project partner CERTH presented the Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT) for the first time, showcasing its interdisciplinary approach (**Figure 38**).

Figure 38 Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project at the PETRA' 2024 Conference

8. NeuroconexiON's Second Edition (13 November 2024, Spain)

- Dr Monica Kurtis (FIN) presented the project and its digital health solutions for early detection, progression monitoring, and treatment support for Parkinson's (Figure 39).

Figure 39 Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project at the NeuroconexiON: The second edition

9. DSAI 2024 (15 November 2024, Abu Dhabi, UAE)

- Beatriz Alves (FMH) presented the paper "An Agile Co-Creation Approach for Designing a Comprehensive Digital Motor Assessment Test for Parkinson's Disease Patients," highlighting the development of a digital motor assessment tool (Figure 40).

Figure 40 Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project at the DSAI' 2024 Conference

10. The 2nd Healthy Longevity Symposium (21–22 November 2024, Abu Dhabi, UAE)

- Prof. Leontios Hadjileontiadis (AUTH) presented a smartphone-based Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT) tool to assess motor skills in Parkinson's disease patients, and its integration into patient care using advanced technology (**Figure 41**).

Figure 41 Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project at the 2nd Healthy Longevity Symposium

3.3.2 Business and industry events

Business, industry and EXPO events are key opportunities to share the AI-PROGNOSIS project's vision and connect with industry stakeholders.

During the reporting period, AI-PROGNOSIS was showcased at Medica 2023¹⁶, held from 13-16 November in Düsseldorf, Germany. Representatives from INTRA and AUTH presented the project at this leading international trade fair, which brought together over 81,000 attendees and 4,500 exhibitors from across the world. MEDICA is known for attracting leading figures from business, research, and politics and providing a high-profile platform for innovative projects.

The project partners also took part in several business-focused events aimed at exploring collaboration opportunities, including:

- A meeting with Pfizer's Centre for Digital Innovation (CDI) in Thessaloniki, Greece, on 13 December 2023.
- A session with Sonova International in Thessaloniki, Greece, on 30 August 2024, focused on hearing care and digital health.
- A discussion with KOIOS Care in Leuven, Belgium, on 19 January 2024, about using AI in healthcare.
- An online meeting with Neuralight on 11 June 2024 to discuss neuro-assessment tools.
- A meeting with ELPEN Pharmaceutical Co. in Athens, Greece, on 3 December 2024.

These events allowed AI-PROGNOSIS to share its vision, gather insights, and build valuable partnerships with industry leaders.

¹⁶ MEDICA Trade fair, <https://www.medica-tradefair.com/>

3.3.3 Workshops, seminars, and special sessions

In June 2024, an overview of the AI-PROGNOSIS project and ongoing research on digital motor skill assessment was presented to PhD students from Faculdade de Motricidade Humana (Lisbon, Portugal) in the context of the Physical Activity and Health program.

In June 2024, the workshop “AGENT - Multimodal siGnal sensing/analysis, innovative interactive Environments, and persoNalized behavioral modeling for improving qualiTy-of-life” has been organised at PETRA 2024¹⁷. This workshop was organised by the CERTH, AUTH and FMH-ULisboa in cooperation with the AI-PROGNOSIS and iPROLEPSIS¹⁸ projects. It focused on novel technologies applied in real or virtual environments and aim to enhance the quality of daily living, especially for people with disabilities or patients suffering from chronic conditions.

In November 2024, the AI-PROGNOSIS project was presented as part of the “Neuroscience and Neurodegeneration” MSc programme at AUTH in Thessaloniki, Greece. The presentation, delivered during the lecture “The contribution of new technologies in the diagnosis and treatment of Parkinsonian syndromes”, provided an overview of the project’s contributions to using advanced technologies in Parkinson’s care. This session engaged 30 postgraduate students specialising in health and life sciences, fostering an academic understanding of AI-driven healthcare solutions.

In May 2024, during Europe Biobank Week in Vienna, Austria, Anna Clareborn (UU) delivered a presentation highlighting the integration of the six core principles of patient involvement into AI-PROGNOSIS activities (**Figure 42**). This presentation showcased the project as a best-practice case study, demonstrating its commitment to co-creation and patient-centric approaches in digital health innovation.

Figure 42 Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project activities at the Europe Biobank Week 2024

Additionally, in October 2024 Anna Clareborn (UU) presented the AI-PROGNOSIS project at the Precision Medicine Networking Forum (PMNET) in Riga, Latvia. This event provided a platform for discussing advancements in digital health solutions and facilitated the exchange of ideas with stakeholders from healthcare and research communities.

3.3.4 Demo sessions to stakeholders

Demo sessions play an important role in AI-PROGNOSIS's dissemination strategy, aimed at increasing awareness of the project's solutions and gathering valuable feedback from end-

¹⁷ PETRA 2024, <http://www.petrae.org/workshops/AGENT.html>

¹⁸ <https://www.iprolepsis.eu/>

users, healthcare enablers, and industry stakeholders. These sessions are planned to commence from M18, aligning with the availability of alpha versions of the project's digital tools. A total of 6 demo sessions are foreseen, ensuring broad engagement and continuous refinement of the tools based on stakeholder input.

During the reporting period, no demo sessions were conducted. However, 2 initial co-creation sessions were held, involving representatives of patients with PD who contributed feedback on the project's digital tools, laying the groundwork for future demo sessions.

The first co-creation session, conducted on 8 April 2024, focused on refining the active motor tests component intended for integration into the AI-PROGNOSIS app. Participants reviewed the tool's features and design, offering critical feedback on usability and functionality. This interaction allowed stakeholders to influence the development of the Comprehensive Motor Function Test (CMFT), ensuring its relevance to real-world needs. Feedback from the session highlighted key areas for improvement in test design and user experience, helping align the tool with the expectations and requirements of end-users (**Figure 43**).

Figure 43 Co-Creation workshop for CMFT

The second co-creation session, held on 22–23 October 2024, took the form of focused workshops with the AI-PROGNOSIS Patient Panel (**Figure 44**). Eight PD patients from France, Germany, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and the UK participated, contributing insights to shape the mAI-Care app. The workshops focused on reviewing proposed data visualisations and evaluating the app's design and usability. Feedback from the patient panel was helpful in refining the app's features, particularly with regard to user experience and interface design. The insights gathered guided decisions on data visualisation features and future improvements, ensuring the app's accessibility and effectiveness for its intended users.

Figure 44 Co-Creation workshop for mAI-Care App UI/UX design

These sessions mark the initial phase of engaging stakeholders in demo-style interactions, focusing on early-stage tools and gathering feedback to refine their development. Future sessions will continue to showcase advanced versions of the tools, ensuring alignment with stakeholder needs and expectations.

4 Educational material

4.1.1 Educational content development strategy

The strategy for the development of educational content in AI-PROGNOSIS outlined below has the main purpose of helping project partners develop impactful and engaging educational content for the public, with a focus on PD and the AI-enabled digital health tools developed in AI-PROGNOSIS. The initiative aims to raise awareness, improve health literacy, and foster trust in emerging technologies through tailored, accessible, and interactive materials.

Main objectives

The main objectives of the educational content are to:

- Educate the general public on PD, emphasising early detection, treatment benefits, and lifestyle management.
- Enhance understanding of AI in healthcare, focusing on its role in improving disease management and health outcomes.
- Address the needs and concerns of both individuals with and without PD.
- Build a community of informed stakeholders through open, accessible educational resources.

Stakeholder collaboration and approval

The development process has involved a multidisciplinary approach to stakeholder collaboration. Relevant stakeholders, internal or external to the project have been invited to

provide accuracy checks for developed educational content. Key stakeholder groups involved include:

- **Persons with PD:** These stakeholders are involved to validate content relevance and ensure it meets users' needs.
- **Healthcare professionals (HCPs):** These stakeholders provide expert insights into clinical aspects of PD and actionable recommendations.

Additionally, where needed:

- **Technical professionals:** These stakeholders provide expert insights into the technical aspects of the AI-PROGNOSIS tools.

All educational content typically undergoes two rounds of approval with input from two separate stakeholder groups. When evaluating the materials, they consider checklists, more specifically general, article-specific, and multimedia-specific, which help ensure the materials meet the highest standards.

The general checklist reflects the most basic evaluation criteria. It focuses on whether the content is engaging, raises awareness about PD, improves health literacy, and is tailored for individuals with the disease, those without it, or both (**Figure 45**).

The figure shows a checklist with four items, each in a white rounded rectangle on a blue background. Each item has a checked box on the left and an unchecked box on the right. The items are:

- Is it engaging?
- Does it raise awareness about PD?
- Does it improve health literacy?
- Is it tailored for individuals with the disease, those without it, or both?

Figure 45 General checklist

The article checklist reflects evaluation criteria specific to articles, both for the longer and shorter formats. It focuses on accessibility, informativeness, simplification of complex information, clarity of the target group, and the appropriateness of the message, tone, and content for the intended audience (**Figure 46**).

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Is it accessible?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Is it informative?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Does it simplify complex information/make complex information more accessible?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Is the target group clear?
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Is the message, tone and content appropriate for the target group?

Figure 46 Article checklist

The multimedia checklist reflects evaluation criteria specific to different types of multimedia, such as infographics, diagrams, charts, quizzes, videos, and similar. It focuses on whether the content is interactive, visually engaging, simplifies complex information, clearly identifies the target group, and ensures the message, tone, and content are appropriate for the intended audience (**Figure 47**).

This process ensures the creation of educational materials that are accurate, accessible, and impactful. Accuracy is ensured through expert review by healthcare professionals and technical experts, accessibility is validated through testing with persons with PD, and impactfulness is assessed based on stakeholder feedback on relevance and usability. These collaborative steps ensure the materials meet the highest standards before being shared publicly.

Target audience

Three main target groups have been identified, namely:

- **The general public:** A heterogeneous group, including individuals without a personal connection to PD. This diverse audience spans various age groups, backgrounds, and interests. Their commonality lies in a shared curiosity about PD and a desire for accessible information. The focus should be on raising awareness, dispelling misconceptions, and fostering engagement. Educational content should contribute to a broader understanding of PD within the community.
- **People without PD:** A complex group overlapping both with the general public and people with PD. It includes caregivers, often family members or close friends, who play

The image shows a checklist with five items, each presented in a white rounded rectangle against a blue background. Each item consists of a black square with a white checkmark, followed by a white rounded rectangle containing an unchecked checkbox and the question text.

- Is it interactive, and if not, would it benefit from being interactive?
- Is it visually engaging?
- Does it simplify complex information/make complex information more accessible?
- Is the target group clear?
- Is the message, tone and content appropriate for the target group?

Figure 47 Multimedia checklist

- a vital role in supporting individuals with PD. Those at risk of PD also seek information to understand potential symptoms and risk factors, and some may be caregivers themselves. Educational content should be tailored to meet the diverse needs of this group.
- **People with PD:** Individuals diagnosed with PD form a diverse group facing unique challenges. This group encompasses people of varying ages, backgrounds, and lifestyles who share a common journey of navigating the complexities of PD. Their diverse experiences, needs, and perspectives underscore the importance of providing tailored information and support to enhance their understanding of the condition and empower them in managing their health.

All educational materials are made available under a dedicated section of the AI-PROGNOSIS project website. In terms of future integration into the mAI-Health and mAI-Care apps, selected educational materials will be made available there as well, but with possible modifications to better fit that platform and context.

A structure for educational content formats has been developed and includes the categories described below.

4.1.2 Dictionary entries/short articles

The dictionary entries (up to 200 words) are designed to explain terms commonly used within the AI-PROGNOSIS project (such as on the project website) in a clear and accessible way. Their primary purpose is to provide users with an easy-to-understand resource for navigating complex topics. By highlighting essential terms, the dictionary fosters deeper learning and ensures that website users can engage with the content meaningfully. These entries are crafted to support the project's goal of promoting education on PD, and to make medical and technical language and concepts more approachable.

4.1.3 Long articles

The long articles (up to 400 words) are designed to provide detailed insights into more complex topics central to AI-PROGNOSIS. These articles target key areas of medicine, artificial intelligence, and technology that are relevant to the project's activities. By addressing how the many moving parts of the project apply to the management of PD, they support the AI-PROGNOSIS aim of promoting awareness and making advanced technical concepts more transparent to all stakeholders.

4.1.4 Videos

The videos focus on specific topics in PD in general, as well as the AI-PROGNOSIS project specifically. By presenting the perspectives of various stakeholders involved in PD management and research, the videos allow viewers to hear directly from experts, patients, and contributors from around the world. They provide different perspectives on the same subject, and spotlight subjects in a brief, accessible format.

4.1.5 Quizzes

The quizzes are designed to complement the AI-PROGNOSIS project's educational materials by offering an engaging and interactive way to reinforce learning. Based on the dictionary entries/short articles, long articles, and videos, the quizzes challenge users to test their retention and understanding of key concepts related to PD and the AI-PROGNOSIS project. They are intended to ensure that users can review and apply what they have learned in a meaningful way. The quizzes support the goal of making complex medical and technical concepts approachable while encouraging deeper engagement with the content.

4.1.6 Infographics

The infographics are designed to simplify and visualize the more complex learning materials presented in the project. By distilling information from the dictionary entries/short articles, long articles, and videos into clear and visually engaging formats, the infographics make the key concepts easier to understand and remember. They are intended to be visually appealing and user friendly, and to provide a quick overview of key facts related to PD and the AI-PROGNOSIS.

4.1.7 Available educational content

The following content has been added to the Learning hub:

- **Dictionary entry on Motor Symptoms¹⁹**: Provides a brief explanation of motor symptoms, such as stiffness, tremor, and slowness of movement, commonly observed in Parkinson's disease. The dictionary is available in the Dictionary section under the Learning Hub on the website.
- **Article on Sex and Gender Impact on PD²⁰**: Explores how sex and gender differences influence the progression, diagnosis, and management of PD. The article is available on Article section under the Learning Hub on the website.
- **Interactive Quiz²¹**: Offers an engaging way for users to test their knowledge of Parkinson's disease, with questions covering symptoms, statistics, and related facts. The Quiz is available on Quiz section under the Learning Hub on the website.
- **Video "Motor Symptoms in Parkinson's Disease: The Clinical Perspective"²²**: This video provides HCP's insights into the motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease,

¹⁹ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/dictionary>

²⁰ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/articles>

²¹ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/quiz>

²² Videos section on the website, [Video | AI-PROGNOSIS](#)

including tremor, slowness, rigidity and their role in diagnosis. The video is available on Videos section under the Learning Hub on the website.

The educational content available on the website is presented below in **Figure 48**.

Figure 48 PD educational content on the AI-PROGNOSIS website

The launch of the Learning Hub section and the first quiz on the website in October 2024 resulted in a noticeable increase in website traffic (**Figure 14**), with visitors reaching 522 for that month.

The additional content that has been currently prepared but pending approval includes two articles and a new quiz.

The first article provides an overview of the scientific publication "*A.I. Robustness: A Human-Centered Perspective on Technological Challenges and Opportunities*" by Tocchetti, A. et al. (available at [2210.08906] [A.I. Robustness: a Human-Centered Perspective on Technological Challenges and Opportunities](#)), which explores challenges in AI reliability and highlights the importance of integrating human insights into AI development.

The second article offers an overview of the scientific publication "*Trust and Trustworthiness in AI Ethics*" by Reinhardt, K. (available at [Trust and trustworthiness in AI ethics | AI and Ethics](#)), which discusses the complexities of trust in AI and the ethical considerations surrounding AI development.

Additionally, a new quiz on the prodromal stage and early signs of PD will help users test their knowledge on the disease's early symptoms and potential misdiagnoses. These additions will enhance the Learning Hub once approved.

5 Clustering and networking activities

Clustering and networking activities (the subject of T6.2) focus on establishing meaningful connections with stakeholders, similar projects, and relevant initiatives. These activities aim to raise awareness, facilitate knowledge exchange, and effectively communicate the project's vision and outcomes to key stakeholder groups, including policymakers, HCPs, PD organisations, and private companies.

An initial list of relevant research and innovation (R&I) projects and initiatives for clustering and networking was provided in D6.2, “Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan” (submitted in M5). During the M1–M18 period, AI-PROGNOSIS has actively engaged in various clustering and networking efforts, including:

- Forming a partnership with the Digital Health Uptake project,
- Collaborating with sister projects,
- Applying for Horizon Result Booster services, and
- Engaging in partner-led networking activities within existing networks.

These activities, described in detail in sections **5.1.1-5.1.4.**, underline AI-PROGNOSIS's commitment to fostering collaboration and amplifying its impact through strategic connections.

5.1.1 Establishment of a partnership with the Digital Health Uptake project

The Digital Health Uptake (DHU) project²³, funded through the Digital Europe Programme, is dedicated to aligning policies, strategies, instruments, and activities to promote the adoption of digital health solutions and services across Europe. DHU's efforts are categorised into three key aspects: RADAR, KNOWLEDGE COMMUNITY, and ACCELERATOR.

In the context of building a digital health ecosystem, which is a shared goal of both AI-PROGNOSIS and DHU, the projects commenced their interaction as of M4. Collaboration possibilities and synergies between the DHU project and AI-PROGNOSIS were discussed and agreed upon by the project coordinator of the AI-PROGNOSIS project (Prof. Leontios Hadjileontiadis), and the representative of Empirica²⁴, the coordinating organisation of the DHU project (Ms. Anett Ruszanov). Mutual promotion of relevant news and events through websites, newsletters, and social media, as well as potential co-organisation of events, were among the identified areas of collaboration.

As part of this collaboration, the AI-PROGNOSIS project was featured on the DHU website²⁵ (**Figure 49**). Updates about AI-PROGNOSIS appeared in the DHU newsletters, including the September 2024 and December 2023 editions (**Figure 50**). Likewise, the DHU project has been featured in AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination channels, including its website, social media, and newsletters published in November 2023²⁶ and September 2024²⁷ (**Figure 51**).

²³ <https://digitalhealthuptake.eu/>

²⁴ <https://empirica.com/>

²⁵ Digital Health Uptake project website, <https://digitalhealthuptake.eu/synergies/ai-prognosis-project/>

²⁶ The AI-PROGNOSIS November 2023 issue, https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/_files/ugd/ea957b_42a4ab489af94ddabedab66ce231fba7.pdf

²⁷ The AI-PROGNOSIS September 2024 issue, https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/_files/ugd/981fae_59837452a5cf447bbe84da7c1e57b31a.pdf

Figure 49 AI-PROGNOSIS on the DHU website

Figure 50 AI-PROGNOSIS in the DHU newsletters

Figure 51 DHU on the AI-PROGNOSIS website, social media and newsletters

Additionally, the mAI-Health app (study version) has been registered on the DHU Radar Repository²⁸. This platform serves as a one-stop-shop catalogue for digital health resources – referred to as "practices" – focusing on digital health solutions, strategies, policies, tools, and related resources that support the uptake of digital health practices across Europe. Currently, the repository features over 100 practices, and integrating the mAI-Health app into this resource is anticipated to further enhance its visibility and accessibility.

5.1.2 Collaboration with sister projects

In M9, the establishment of an ecosystem of initiatives began, consisting of projects funded under the call HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHLTH-01-04. These projects are the following:

- AI-PROGNOSIS,
- STRATIFYHF,
- TRUSTING,
- ARISTOTELES,
- AI-POD,
- SmartCHANGE,
- VASCUL-AID,
- ARTILERY,
- AI4HF and
- TRUSTroke.

AI-PROGNOSIS initiated contact with these projects, exchanging communication materials to be featured on each project's website to raise awareness of the cluster's vision. As a result, a Networking²⁹ subsection was created on the AI-PROGNOSIS website (Figure 52), featuring information about sister projects. In M16, a social media campaign was launched to further introduce sister projects and enhance visibility (Figure 53).

Starting from M15, collaborative efforts intensified with the commencement of the Stay Healthy Cluster Communication and Dissemination Task Force meetings. Two online meetings were held in September and November 2024, engaging representatives from multiple projects to

²⁸ The DHU Radar Repository, <https://digitalhealthuptake.eu/radar-repository/mai-health-study-version/>

²⁹ Networking subsection, AI-PROGNOSIS website, <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/networking>

Figure 52 AI-PROGNOSIS website - Networking subsection

explore synergies, joint branding, and dissemination activities. Key actions and outcomes included:

- Creating a mailing list for streamlined communication;
- Discussing proposals for common branding creation;
- Planning joint dissemination activities, such as coordinated social media campaigns, newsletters, and participation in events like the ADRa conference; and
- Exploring co-organisation of events, including the AI-PROGNOSIS-led workshop "Trustworthy AI in Digital Health: From Guidelines to Practice," scheduled for the Health Data Summit in March 2025.

These efforts underline AI-PROGNOSIS's commitment to fostering collaboration within the sister projects, enhancing the impact of digital health innovations across Europe.

Figure 53 Social media campaign introducing sister projects

5.1.3 Horizon Results Booster services – Portfolio dissemination

In M11, AI-PROGNOSIS applied for the Horizon Results Booster (HRB)³⁰ services, a European Commission initiative to maximise the impact of publicly funded research. The project applied for Module A, focused on creating a portfolio of R&I project results, and Module C, aimed at improving the project’s exploitation strategy.

By utilising HRB services, AI-PROGNOSIS seeks to increase its visibility and impact by showcasing tangible outcomes and connecting with similar EU-funded projects. This approach fosters knowledge exchange, synergies, and potential partnerships to advance healthcare innovation.

As of the deliverable preparation, a cluster of 5 projects has been formed including AI-PROGNOSIS, iPROLEPSIS, HIPPOCRATES, REBECCA and AutoPiX. With HRB transitioning to HRB2 (Booster) in M17, AI-PROGNOSIS is awaiting the initiation of service delivery.

5.1.4 Networking activities of partners

AI-PROGNOSIS partners actively engaged in networking activities with researchers, industry, and other projects to share knowledge and create collaboration opportunities.

Key initiatives include:

- A meeting with Pfizer's Centre for Digital Innovation (CDI) in Thessaloniki, Greece, on 13 December 2023. This meeting facilitated discussions on collaborative opportunities, with a focus on innovation and the potential application of AI technologies in healthcare.

³⁰ Horizon Result Booster, <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

- Participation in the Plenary Meeting 3 of the iPROLEPSIS Horizon Europe project, held on 12 November 2023 in Rotterdam, the Netherlands. This clustering activity emphasised knowledge sharing and collaboration among European research projects.
- Discussions with KOIOS Care in Leuven, Belgium, on 19 January 2024, highlighting the integration of AI technologies into clinical and healthcare settings.
- An online meeting with Neuralight on 11 June 2024, focusing on neuro-assessment tools and the application of AI in neurological research.
- Engagement with Sonova International in Thessaloniki, Greece, on 30 August 2024, to explore partnerships in digital health technologies.
- A meeting with ELPEN Pharmaceutical Co. in Athens, Greece, on 3 December 2024 to explore the potential of motor function digital biomarkers as clinical trial endpoints.

These activities reflect AI-PROGNOSIS’s efforts to connect with stakeholders, learn from others, and create partnerships to drive innovation in healthcare.

6 Dissemination and communication performance (KPIs)

Monitoring the impact of the different dissemination and communication activities involves systematic data collection and reporting from all partners. This approach helps assess the success of the dissemination and communication strategy outlined in deliverable D6.2.

As set in D6.2, the communication and dissemination objectives are to be achieved through the activities of all partners: individually, through each partner’s entity activities, and collectively, through the partner’s contribution to the global strategy. The goal is to reach the project’s stakeholders and build the AI-PROGNOSIS community.

KPIs were defined in the Description of the Action (DoA) to measure the impact of each dissemination and communication activity. Sections 3 and 5 of this deliverable provide an overview of activities conducted from M1 to M18. The current section summarises these efforts, as presented in **Table 4**.

Table 4 Target and reached KPIs for M1-M18

Dissemination and communication actions	What	When	Target KPI	Reached KPI M1-M18
Publications	Peer-reviewed journals	From M18, when solid scientific results are available	20 publications	4 scientific publications (2 of them in peer-reviewed journals)
	Business Magazines		4 publications	0
Event participation	Scientific conference presentations/posters	From M12, when initial scientific	20 presentations/posters	10

Dissemination and communication actions	What	When	Target KPI	Reached KPI M1-M18
	Business/Industry events and EXPOs stands/booths	results are available	3 events	5 (presence in 1 booth in MEDICA 2023)
	Workshops/ Special sessions/ Seminars	From M18, when solid scientific results are available	8 events 50 expected attendees	5 / ~60 attendees
	Demo sessions to stakeholders	From M18, when alpha versions of tools are available	6 demo sessions	0 demo sessions; 2 co-creation workshops
Media presence	Newsletters	From M4 every three months	1000 subscribers	4 newsletters; 407 subscribers
	Website/blog posts	From M3	4 posts/month 1000 visitors/month	Av. 4 posts per month; Av. 183 visitors/month
	Social media posts	From M1	2 posts/week 2000 followers	Av. 2 post/week 1107 followers
	Major media (TV/radio) presence	From M6, when tangible results are produced	5 presences in national media	0
2 presences in EU-level media			0	
Networking and clustering events			≥4 networking/joint initiatives	5 networking meetings/ 2 online meetings with sister projects / Participation in 3 networking initiatives: DHU, Sister projects' cluster, Horizon Booster Services – Portfolio dissemination cluster)

Table 4 shows a mixed level of progress toward the dissemination and communication KPIs, which reflect the phased nature of project activities. At M18 of the 48-month duration, progress

in certain areas is on track or ahead of schedule, while other areas are expected to accelerate as the project matures and generates more tangible results.

The project has actively participated in 10 scientific conferences and 5 business and industry events (with a booth presence at one of them). Social media and newsletter outreach have also progressed steadily, with 407 newsletter subscribers, 1,107 social media followers, and consistent posting activity.

Peer-reviewed publications are underway, with 4 completed to date and 5 more planned for submission, reflecting the ongoing generation of solid scientific results. Two of the four publications made so far are in peer-reviewed journals. Additionally, 5 workshops have been organised or attended to share insights, while 2 co-creation workshops have been conducted, laying a foundation for future demo sessions to stakeholders as tools are developed.

Areas such as media presence and website traffic require additional focus to meet the targets set for the entire project duration. Website activity, which averages 183 monthly visitors, needs to grow to reach the target of 1,000 visitors per month. Media appearances, both at national and EU levels, have yet to be achieved, highlighting an area for intensified efforts moving forward.

The strategy outlined in D6.2 has provided a strong starting point for these activities. Progress has been made in social media engagement, clustering efforts, and scientific conference participation. However, gaps remain in media visibility and online engagement metrics. To address these challenges, AI-PROGNOSIS will explore new outreach methods, such as utilising EC dissemination and communication platforms, creating short videos for social media, and incorporating interactive graphics to better connect with audiences. The project will also enhance collaboration with sister projects to increase visibility and impact. The strategy will remain flexible and be updated regularly to align with project goals and stakeholder needs.

Progress updates will be detailed in the upcoming deliverables, D6.5 “Midterm report on project visibility and educational material” (M32) and D6.6 “Final report on project visibility and educational material” (M48). This adaptive approach will help ensure the project continues to align its efforts with long-term visibility and communication objectives while maximising its overall impact.

7 Conclusions

The first report on project visibility and educational material, D6.3, accounts for the tasks carried out, communication and dissemination activities undertaken, as well as the progress achieved in developing educational content. It highlights the progress made by the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium up to M18. Key achievements include:

- **Project identity:** A cohesive project identity, including logos, banners, and other branding materials, has ensured a unified and recognisable presence across all dissemination and communication channels.
- **Dissemination and communication:** The project has successfully promoted updates and achievements and engaged with a wide range of stakeholders by using media platforms and dissemination channels, such as social media, newsletters, the project website, interviews and conferences. 4 peer-reviewed publications have been published, showcasing the project's initial scientific contributions.

- **Stakeholder engagement:** Targeted communication activities have made project outputs visible to various stakeholders, including researchers, HCPs, industry representatives, people with PD and the general public.
- **Development of educational materials:** The project has introduced a Learning Hub on its website, offering engaging and interactive materials to raise awareness about PD and improve health literacy. These materials include dictionary entries, long articles, videos, quizzes, and infographics, designed to make complex medical and technical concepts more accessible. The Learning Hub provides resources tailored to the general public, people without PD, and people with PD. All content undergoes a rigorous review process by relevant stakeholders, including HCPs and individuals with Parkinson's, to ensure accuracy, accessibility, and relevance. The launch of the Learning Hub and its first quiz in October 2024 has already positively impacted visibility metrics, with a notable increase in website traffic. The additional content, including new articles and quizzes, is expected to further enhance the Learning Hub and continue to improve visibility metrics.
- **Networking and clustering:** Various networking activities have been initiated to foster collaboration, raise awareness, exchange knowledge, and communicate the project's vision and outcomes to key stakeholder groups. AI-PROGNOSIS has established a partnership with the DHU project and strengthened collaboration with other projects funded under the HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHLTH-01-04 call. Additionally, the mAI-Health app has been registered on the DHU Radar Repository, a platform showcasing digital health practices across Europe. This registration enhances the app's visibility and accessibility, highlighting its potential impact within the digital health ecosystem. Booster services are planned to be utilised to support joint dissemination activities for a cluster formed of the AI-PROGNOSIS, iPROLEPSIS, REBECCA, HIPPOCRATES, and AutoPiX projects. Networking efforts have also included meetings with industry leaders such as Pfizer's CDI, Sonova International, KOIOS Care, Neuralight, and ELPEN Pharmaceutical Co., as well as participation in the iPROLEPSIS Horizon Europe project Plenary meeting.
- **Performance evaluation:** KPIs have been used to track the impact of communication and dissemination efforts. Progress has been strong in areas such as scientific conferences, business events, and social media outreach, with some targets already exceeded. Publications and workshops are progressing as planned, though certain areas like media presence and website traffic require additional attention. Moving forward, efforts will focus on expanding media outreach, increasing publications, and enhancing stakeholder engagement to meet long-term project objectives.

The AI-PROGNOSIS project has successfully established a strong foundation for visibility, stakeholder engagement, and the development of educational content during the first M18. Moving forward, efforts will focus on enhancing dissemination and communication activities, expanding the stakeholder network, and enriching the educational content available through the Learning Hub. Continued collaboration with sister projects and strategic planning will ensure the project's visibility is maintained and its impact maximised. Future reports, including deliverables D6.5 and D6.6, will provide further updates on the project's progress and impact.